

PERCEIVED TEACHING COMPETENCY LEVEL: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION PROGRAMS

Erika Jane S. Cacaldo, LPT, Suzette Ceniza, LPT, MAEd, Jerry A. Pariscal, LPT,
Dexter D. Saycon, LPT, Menche A. Tuting, LPT, Jeckson B. Repollo, LPT, MAEd-Fil,
Cristina P. Calisang, EdD

Metro Dumaguete College, Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, 6200, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14310142>

ABSTRACT

This study explores the perceived teaching competency level of teachers as a basis for intervention programs. Conducted at Metro Dumaguete College, the respondents comprised 345 students from various academic levels. A validated self-made survey questionnaire was utilized as the primary tool for data collection. Statistical tools such as mean, Pearson's Correlation Coefficient (r), and Weighted Mean were employed to analyze the findings. The study assessed the perceived teaching competency level in four areas: instructional delivery, classroom management, commitment, and teaching for independent learning. Results indicated that students perceived their teachers as highly competent in instructional delivery and classroom management, particularly in demonstrating mastery of the subject matter, structuring teaching-learning contexts, and encouraging meaningful engagement. Teachers were also rated as highly committed, especially in terms of punctuality, preparedness, and addressing diverse student needs. Teaching for independent learning was positively perceived, with teachers fostering innovation and inquiry while showing potential areas for improvement in promoting self-directed learning. The academic performance of students across different academic levels was evaluated, showing high overall achievement in both Diploma and Bachelor programs, as well as Senior High School. However, findings revealed no significant relationship between the teachers' perceived teaching competency level and students' academic performance. These insights highlight the need for targeted intervention programs to further enhance teaching practices and support continuous improvement in educational outcomes.

Keywords: *teaching competency, instructional delivery, classroom management, teaching commitment, independent learning, academic performance, intervention programs*

INTRODUCTION

The global education system faces significant challenges as it strives to meet the demands of an increasingly interconnected and fast-evolving world. According to UNESCO (2023), the teaching profession is at a critical juncture, with millions of students globally experiencing a shortage of qualified and competent educators. The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated this issue by exposing gaps in teaching preparedness and competency, particularly in adapting to remote and hybrid learning models. Additionally, Darling-Hammond, et al. (2020), emphasize that equipping teachers with the necessary competencies is pivotal in addressing global disparities in education, ensuring inclusive and quality learning for all students. Teachers need to continuously improve their competency levels to address these challenges and adapt to rapid technological advancements and the dynamic nature of modern education. According to Kim, et al. (2019), to create 21st-century learners, teachers must focus on developing 21st-century skills, re-conceptualizing learning content, and attending timely and relevant seminars. To achieve this, teachers have adopted constructivist approaches to classroom practices, focusing on student-centered learning and innovation. Furthermore, Akram (2019), emphasized that students' perceptions are a critical data source for assessing teacher quality, as they are often linked to academic achievement. Some scholars describe teacher effectiveness, as highlighted by Stronge (2018), in terms of student outcomes, but determining the best metrics for evaluating teacher performance remains a challenge.

Locally, the Philippines also grapples with challenges in teacher competency. A report by the Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS, 2022), highlights that many Filipino educators struggle with limited access to professional development opportunities, particularly in rural and underserved areas. Similarly, Navarro and Santos (2021), note that a lack of modern teaching resources and tools hampers Filipino teachers' ability to deliver effective and innovative instruction, particularly in Science and Mathematics. A study at Cebu Technological University by Padillo, et al. (2021) revealed that teachers need to participate in more training sessions and seminars offered by regional and national organizations to improve their skills and remain current with modern teaching strategies. Teachers must employ appropriate methods and strategies to ensure that students acquire essential knowledge and skills. This demonstrates that competent teachers can effectively deliver quality education, enhance students' higher-order thinking skills, and improve performance both inside and outside the classroom (Gamayao & Binas, 2021). While Francisco and Celon (2020) argue that teaching competencies influence planning, instruction, and assessment, their combined effects on academic performance are not always significant, highlighting the need for sustained professional development.

Previous studies have focused only on the relationship between teaching competencies and professional development activities (Padillo et al., 2021), which proves teachers' teaching competencies and professional development activities have no relationship. The study investigated the teaching competency of teachers but only focused on professional development activities. Furthermore, it is substantial to draw implications from a study that examines the perceived impact of teaching competency level on the academic performances of the students.

In this regard, the researchers of the current study wanted to further investigate how the teachers' competencies can really affect the academic performance of the students. Although some researchers have already examined the teachers' performance in relation to the academic performance of the students, it does not focus on the teachers' competencies affecting the students' academic performance. Thus, the researchers decided to pursue this study with the intent to identify and compare the academic performances of the students and competencies of the teachers at the Metro Dumaguete College (MDC) campus.

Research Questions

The purpose of this research undertaking is to determine the teaching competency level of teachers in Metro Dumaguete College Inc. in relation to the students' academic performance during the first semester of the academic year 2023- 2024. Specifically, this study intends to examine and answer the following questions:

1. What is the perceived teaching competency level of teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1. Instructional Delivery;
 - 1.2. Classroom Management;
 - 1.3. Commitment; and
 - 1.4. Teaching for Independent Learning?
2. What is the student's academic performance for the first semester in S.Y. 2023-2024?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' perceived teaching competency level and students' academic performances?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-quantitative approach to investigate the extent to which teachers' competencies influence the academic performance of students at Metro Dumaguete College. A descriptive-correlational design was used to provide a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between students' academic performance and their perceptions of their teachers' competency levels in key areas such as instructional delivery, classroom management, commitment, and promoting independent learning.

This approach also enabled the comparison of student academic performance across different educational levels.

The primary tool for data collection was a survey questionnaire. The instrument was structured to measure the extent of students' perceptions of their teachers' competencies in delivering instruction, managing classrooms, demonstrating professional commitment, and facilitating independent learning. Additionally, it collected data on the academic performance of students in various programs to analyze its relationship with perceived teaching competency levels.

The collected data were analyzed to determine patterns and correlations between the perceived competency levels of teachers and the academic performance of students. The findings aimed to provide insights into the effectiveness of teaching practices and the role of teacher competencies in fostering academic success among students.

Research Respondents

The respondents of this study are students from various degree programs and strands at Metro Dumaguete College (MDC), who were selected through random sampling method. Out of the 2515 population, 345 students were chosen as the sample with $e=0.05$. The sample includes students from the BS in Computer Science (19), BS in Information Technology (19), BS in Tourism Management (30), BSBA major in Financial Management (16), BSBA major in Marketing Management (8), BTVTED major in Computer Hardware Servicing (5), Diploma in Digital Arts Technology (61), Diploma in Software Engineering Technology (65), Diploma in Tourism Management (93), and Diploma in Vocational Teacher Education Technology (7). Additionally, students from the ABM Strand (4), GAS Strand (3), HUMSS Strand (10), and TVL (Computer Hardware Servicing & Computer Programming) Strand (4), as well as those in TVL (1), were also included. The procedure for selecting the students is systematic, with guidance from the deans and program coordinators of each department to ensure a diverse and representative sample for the study.

Research Instrument

In gathering important data for the study, the researcher utilized an adapted survey questionnaire. The questionnaire items included in the survey were drawn and adapted from the Negros Oriental State University - Quality Assurance Management Council (NORSU-QUAMC). In the first part, the researcher presented the topic and objectives of the study through a letter. The instructions were made clear for the students to understand immediately. Students also provided important information about themselves regarding their own profiles.

The researcher consulted with the Research Director of Metro Dumaguete College to ensure the validity of the instrument's content. Apart from the Research Director, the researcher also showed it to 3 experts to ensure the quality of the questions. They checked if the aspects included in the indicators were coherent. The suggestions and corrections of the reviewers were carefully considered by the researcher for the

improvement of the entire research and for modifying it based on the questionnaire's validity.

In assessing the certainty of the items, a dry-run was conducted. Thirty students were part of the dry-run. The items were examined in terms of certainty using the Cronbach's alpha test. This was considered an appropriate type of research in the survey, where the items were not measured as right or wrong, and different answers could be given for each item (McMillan & Schumacher, 2001). This was done to prove the reliability of the items within the questionnaire. Based on the results, all items included in the survey questionnaire were found to be reliable as they reached and exceeded the 0.70 level of reliability.

Research procedure

After the initial defense, the researcher integrated all the corrections and suggestions of the panel members. A letter of request to conduct the study was sent to the School President, Dr. Delma P. Manila, requesting permission to conduct the study at Metro Dumaguete College. Upon approval, the signed letter was submitted to the Deans and Program Chairs and teachers of the various programs included in the study.

Once permission was granted, the researcher proceeded to distribute the survey questionnaires to the students. Prior to distribution, the researcher explained to the students the purpose, significance, and objectives of the study to ensure they understood the importance of their participation. After providing the necessary information and clarifications, the questionnaires were handed out to the students.

The collected questionnaires were then processed using MS Excel for data entry. Finally, the researcher conducted a thorough analysis and interpretation of the results to draw conclusions and provide insights based on the study's objectives.

RESULTS

Extent of the Perceived Teaching Competency Level of Teachers in Terms of Instructional Delivery (n = 345)

	Classrooms	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	The extent of Competency Level
1.	Demonstrates mastery of the subject matter (explain the subject matter without relying solely on the textbook or ppt).	4.48	Always	Very High
2.	Deepens the explanation of the lessons by providing enough examples.	4.57	Always	Very High
3.	Explains the relevance of the topics to the previous lessons and relates the subject matter to relevant issues and/or daily life activities.	4.52	Always	Very High
4.	Demonstrates up-to-date knowledge and/or awareness on current trends and issues of the subject by giving relevant examples.	4.49	Always	Very High
5.	Brings up difficulties and problems related to the discussion's topic/s.	4.19	Often	High
6.	Employs suitable teaching and learning resources, including ICT, organizes, develops, and uses them to meet learning objectives.	4.41	Always	Very High
7.	Integrates lesson to practical circumstances and learning intents/purposes of students.	4.5	Always	Very High

8.	The teacher's facilitating skills stimulates discussion in different ways such as:			
a.	Probing for student's understanding;			
b.	Helping students articulate their ideas and thinking process;			
c.	Promoting growth mindset and problem solving;	4.54	Always	Very High
d.	Facilitating factual recall			
e.	Encouraging convergent and divergent thinking,			
f.	Stimulating curiosity; and			
g.	Helping students ask questions.			
h.	Promoting metacognition			
Composite		4.46	Always	Very High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Competency Level (ECL)
	4.21 - 5.00	Always	Very High
	3.41 - 4.20	Often	High
	2.61 - 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Seldom	Minimal
	1.00 - 1.80	Never	Not at All

Table 1.1 above shows the students' perception of the extent of the teachers' teaching competency level in the aspect of instructional delivery, specifically in terms of demonstrating mastery of the subject matter, explaining lessons elaborately, relating topics to relevant issues, demonstrating up-to-date knowledge and/or awareness, addressing students' difficulties and problems, employing suitable teacher-learning resources, integrating practical real-world circumstances, and facilitating skills.

Table 1.2
Extent of the Perceived Teaching Competency Level of Teachers in terms of Classroom Management (n = 345)

Classrooms	$\bar{w}\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Extent of Competency Level
1. Provides students with the opportunity to meaningfully contribute students' understanding (for instance, by dividing into dyads, triads, buzz/task groups, or cooperative teams).	4.59	Always	Very High
2. Assumes responsibilities as a facilitator, resource person, coach, inquisitor, referee, in drawing students to contribute to knowledge and understanding of the concepts at hand.	4.48	Always	Very High
3. Designs and implements learning and teaching conditions and experience that promote healthy exchange of ideas and thinking.	4.5	Always	Very High
4. Structures/re-structures learning and teaching-learning context to enhance attainment of learning objectives.	4.38	Always	Very High
5. Stresses the need of encouraging good conduct by giving varied praises, and rewards to the class.	4.32	Always	Very High
6. Address challenging behaviors inside the classroom and maintain a positive and inclusive learning environment by staying calm and neutral and, assess the situation in a positive manner.	4.46	Always	Very High
7. Use of instructional materials (audio/video materials: film showing, computer aided instruction and etc.) to reinforce learning process.	4.43	Always	Very High
Composite	4.45	Always	Very High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Competency Level (ECL)
	4.21 - 5.00	Always	Very High
	3.41 - 4.20	Often	High
	2.61 - 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
	1.81 - 2.60	Seldom	Minimal

Table 1.2 presents the extent to which students perceived their teachers' competency level in terms of classroom management based on various indicators such as providing opportunities for students' meaningful understanding, assuming varied responsibilities to draw students' knowledge and understanding, designing and implementing teaching-learning experiences, structuring of teaching-learning context, encouraging good conduct, addressing challenges, and using of instructional materials.

Table 1.3

Extent of the Perceived Teaching Competency Level of Teachers in terms of Commitment (n = 345)

Classrooms		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Extent of Competency Level
1.	Demonstrates sensitivity to students' ability to absorb content information.	4.38	Always	Very High
2.	Integrates sensitivity to his/her learning objectives with those of the learners in a collaborative process.	4.41	Always	Very High
3.	Makes himself/herself available to students beyond official teaching hours.	4.43	Always	Very High
4.	Regularly comes to class on time, well-groomed and well-prepared and dismisses the class on time.	4.5	Always	Very High
5.	Synchronizes the demands of the learner with external and internal enabling groups.	4.43	Always	Very High
6.	Supplements available resources.	4.4	Always	Very High
7.	Keeps accurate records to students' performance and prompt submission of the students' outputs.	4.54	Always	Very High
Composite		4.44	Always	Very High
Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)		Extent of Competency Level (ECL)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always		Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Often		High
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes		Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Seldom		Minimal
	1.00 – 1.80	Never		Not at All

Table 1.3 displays students' perceptions of the competency level among their teachers in the aspect of commitment which is measured by the following indicators, namely demonstrating sensitivity towards students' learning capacity, integrating collaborative learning, making oneself available beyond working hours, upholding punctuality and preparedness, synchronizing students' diverse needs, diligently monitoring students' performance and submission of outputs.

Table 1.4

Extent of the Perceived Teaching Competency Level of Teachers in terms of Teaching for Independent Learning (n = 345)

Classrooms		$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Extent of Competency Level
1.	Creates teaching strategies that allow students to practice using concepts they need to understand (e.g., interactive discussion, collaboration, and independent learning.)	4.56	Always	Very High
2.	Enhances students' self-esteem and/or gives due recognition to students' performance/potentials.	4.52	Always	Very High
3.	Allows students to think independently and make their own decisions and holding them accountable for their performance based largely on their success in executing decisions.	4.49	Always	Very High
4.	Encourages students to learn beyond what is required and help and guide the students how to apply the concepts learned accountable for their performance.	4.57	Always	Very High

5.	Gives students choices and control over their learning by allowing them to choose topics, projects, or assignments when possible.	4.38	Always	Very High
6.	Help students develop metacognitive skills, such as self-awareness & self-monitoring, and teach them how to plan.	4.52	Always	Very High
7.	Encourage students to ask questions and provide opportunities for them to analyze information, solve problems, and make informed decisions.	4.58	Always	Very High
8.	Design lessons that revolve around inquiry and exploration.	4.46	Always	Very High
Composite		4.51	Always	Very High

Legend:	Scale	Verbal Description (VD)	Extent of Competency Level (ECL)
	4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Often	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Seldom	Minimal
	1.0 – 1.80	Never	Not at All

Table 1.4 shows the students' perception of the extent of their teachers' teaching competency level in terms of teaching for independent learning which encompasses various indicators such as creating differentiated teaching strategies, enhancing students' self-esteem, allowing students to learn independently, encouraging students to think outside the box while guiding them simultaneously, giving students freedom to take control over their learning, helping students hone their metacognition, eliciting students' responses and questions, and fostering inquiry and innovation in the lessons provided.

Table 2.1
Academic Performance of the Students in Diploma and Bachelor

Grade Descriptors	Range	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	1.0 - 1.3	89	27.6%
Very Good	1.4 - 1.7	123	38.1%
Good	1.8 - 2.1	48	14.8%
Average	2.2 - 2.5	30	9.3%
Below Average	2.6 - 3.0	33	10.2%
Total		323	100%

Table 2.1 presents the academic performance of students under the Diploma programs and Baccalaureate degree courses for the first semester in the school year 2023-2024. As reflected in the table below, majority of the student-respondents obtaining 38.1% of the total sample size received a 'Very Good' remark on their grade range (1.4-1.7), followed by 27.6% with a grade range of 1.0-1.3 which received an 'Excellent' remark for their academic performance during the aforementioned school year.

Table 2.2
Academic Performance of the Students in Senior High School

Grade Descriptors	Range	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	90 - 100	13	59.1%
Very Satisfactory	85 - 89	5	22.7%
Satisfactory	80 - 84	3	13.6%
Fairly Satisfactory	75 - 79	1	4.6%
Did Not Meet Expectations	Below 75	0	0
Total		22	100%

Table 2.2 shows the academic performance of Senior High School students during the same school year as mentioned previously. Evidently, majority of the student-respondents encompassing 59.1% of the total number of respondents garnered an

'Outstanding' remark on their grades ranging from 90-100, followed by 22.7% which obtained a grade range from 85-89 receiving a 'Very Satisfactory' remark.

Table 3.1

Relationship between the Teachers' Perceived Teaching Competency Level on Diploma and Bachelor Students' Academic Performance

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Academic Performance				
Instructional Delivery	0.246	0.558	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Classroom Management	0.383	0.349	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Commitment	0.344	0.404	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Teaching for Independent Learning	0.127	0.765	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant

Table 3.1 reflects the relationship between the teachers' perceived teaching competency level and the academic performance of Diploma and Bachelor students. Based on the data, all variables had p-values greater than 0.05, implying no significant relationship exists between the teachers' perceived competency level and students' academic performances.

Table 3.2

Relationship between the Teachers' Perceived Teaching Competency Level on Senior High School Students' Academic Performance

Variables Correlated	Pearson r	p-value	Decision	Remark
Academic Performance				
Instructional Delivery	0.265	0.526	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Classroom Management	0.284	0.495	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Commitment	0.227	0.588	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant
Teaching for Independent Learning	0.339	0.411	Fail to reject H_{01}	Not significant

Table 3.2 shows the relationship between the teachers' perceived teaching competency level and Senior High School students' academic performance. As can be gleaned from the table, all variables had p-values greater than 0.05, implying no significant relationship exists between the teachers' perceived competency level and Senior High School students' academic performances.

DISCUSSION

Extent of the Perceived Teaching Competency Level of Teachers in terms of Instructional Delivery

Table 1.1 shows the students' perception of the extent of their teachers' teaching competency level in the aspect of instructional delivery, specifically in terms of demonstrating mastery of the subject matter, explaining lessons elaborately, relating topics to relevant issues, demonstrating up-to-date knowledge and/or awareness, addressing students' difficulties and problems, employing suitable teacher-learning resources, integrating practical real-word circumstances, and facilitating skills.

The data implies that the very high score for deepening explanation of the lessons by providing enough examples with the highest mean score (\overline{wx}) of 4.57, indicates that teachers are successfully fostering concrete class discussions to better gauge abstract and complex concepts into real-life applications for students to better grasp and understand the lessons. Additionally, the strong perception that the teachers' facilitating skills stimulates discussion in numerous ways obtaining the mean score (\overline{wx}) of 4.54, suggests that teachers are effective in establishing a dynamic and enriching learning environment where students feel valued and encouraged to actively engage and participate in the class. On the other hand, although bringing up difficulties and problems related to the discussion of the topics reached a 'high' ECL remark, but it obtained the lowest mean score (\overline{wx}) of 4.19 which indicates a potential area for improvement to further stimulate the critical thinking and problem-solving skills of students in order for them to actively participate during class discussions by prompting them to analyze, question, and evaluate information rather than passively receiving it.

According to the study conducted by the Metropolitan State University of Denver (2022), student learning is strengthened when concepts are being associated with key attributes that are easy for students to relate with. This is done when teachers provide sufficient examples in various real-life contexts while explaining concepts. Moreover, in today's classroom, teachers play a crucial role as learning facilitators to create a lively and passionate learning environment. In learner-centered teaching, teachers actively facilitate learning by inviting and ensuring the participation of all students to provide a real and authentic learning experience (Suneetha, 2020).

Furthermore, to further establish active participation in the class, teachers are encouraged to bring up difficulties and problems related to the discussion of topics which is a form of Problem-based Learning (PBL), where students can interact collaboratively to solve real-world problems and share varied viewpoints that unequivocally cultivate critical thinking, problem-solving, creativity, and analytical skills. All of which are absolutely essential in the 21st century, as they can enhance both personal and professional life (Lim, 2023).

In conclusion, the high ratings for these indicators suggest emphasis on contextual learning and student-centered approach as learning in context helps students appreciate the relevance of theoretical knowledge and its application to the real-world leading to increased motivation and engagement (Caroll, et al., 2022). Integrating learning with real-world contexts is pivotal in fostering a comprehensive understanding and practical application of knowledge beyond traditional classroom settings. Such contextualization serves to stimulate interest, curiosity, and motivation, thereby enriching the overall learning experience (Caroll, et al., 2022).

Extent of the Perceived Teaching Competency Level of Teachers in terms of Classroom Management

Table 1.2 presents the extent to which students perceived their teachers' competency level in terms of classroom management based on various indicators such

as providing opportunities for students' meaningful understanding, assuming varied responsibilities to draw students' knowledge and understanding, designing and implementing teaching-learning experiences, structuring of teaching-learning context, encouraging good conduct, addressing challenges, and using of instructional materials.

Among the various indicators associated with classroom management which obtained a 'very high' extent of competency level (ECL) remark, it can be noticed that providing opportunities for students' meaningful understanding (e.g. dyads, trials, buzz/task groups, or cooperative teams, etc.) obtained the highest mean score (\overline{wx}) of 4.59, followed by designing and implementing learning and teaching conditions and experience that promote healthy exchange of ideas and thinking which obtained a mean score (\overline{wx}) of 4.5. These findings evidently suggest that teachers are successful in integrating collaborative activities which promotes social interaction among students leading to increased motivation and the establishment of a supportive learning environment where students feel at ease discussing ideas and asking questions. Moreover, working collaboratively enables students to gain exposure to diverse perspectives and problem-solving approaches, expanding their thinking and empowering them to consider alternative viewpoints, ultimately enhancing their overall comprehension.

As postulated by Gates (2018), the implementation of collaborative learning has been demonstrated to not only cultivate higher-order thinking skills in students but also to enhance their confidence and self-esteem as it aims to optimize the educational experience by actively presenting the subject matter while concurrently refining students' social and interpersonal proficiencies. Students acquire the ability to collaborate with diverse learner profiles and cultivate their leadership capabilities. Moreover, Munna and Kalam (2021) further asserted that actively engaging with others consistently leads to heightened participation in the learning process, and sharing ideas, as well as, receiving feedback enhances critical thinking and comprehension.

Overall, the results suggest that an effective classroom management is one that fosters collaborative work among students allowing them to interact with each other by assertively sharing their varied insights without being superior and inferior with one another. This assertion is anchored by the study conducted by the University of Michigan (2021), claiming that effective learning and work thrive on collaboration and social interaction, not competition and isolation. By doing so, teachers are better able to create a supportive learning environment where students feel motivated to learn.

Extent of the Perceived Teaching Competency Level of Teachers in terms of Commitment

Table 1.3 displays students' perceptions of the competency level among their teachers in the aspect of commitment which is measured by the following indicators, namely demonstrating sensitivity towards students' learning capacity, integrating collaborative learning, making oneself available beyond working hours, upholding

punctuality and preparedness, synchronizing students' diverse needs, diligently monitoring students' performance and submission of outputs.

All indicators under teachers' commitment gained a 'Very High' ECL remark which evidently suggests that teachers are ultimately committed on their tasks toward providing quality and equitable education to their students. Among the various indicators, keeping accurate records to students' performance and prompt submission of the students' outputs obtained the highest mean score (\overline{wx}) of 4.54 which significantly implies that teachers are successful in keeping track of students' progress over time. This allows teachers to identify trends, strengths, and areas that need improvement. It also enables the provision of timely interventions and personalized support to students. Additionally, regularly coming to class on time, well-groomed and well-prepared and dismissing the class on time also gained a considerable mean score (\overline{wx}) of 4.5 which suggests that teachers are successful in setting a positive example of discipline and punctuality toward their students which eventually encourage them to observe the same.

According to Aderounmu (2021), keeping records of students' achievements is absolutely crucial to enable both formative assessments and formative teaching. It is by doing so that teachers are able to know which part of their teaching style should they improve and how to enhance it in order to further improve student learning. This is further supported by the study of Anirudh (2021), which claims that maintaining student records helps teachers track student progress, identify weaknesses, and provide personalized feedback for improved growth. Moreover, discipline and punctuality among teachers also hold a significant underpinning in terms of commitment because being on time not only sets a compelling example for students but also creates a highly structured and efficient learning environment. When teachers consistently arrive promptly for classes, it signifies a deep respect for students' time and a steadfast dedication to their profession (Ashraf, 2024).

To conclude based on the data gathered, teachers' commitment is significantly anchored in terms of keeping track students' progress on their academic performance accurately and promptly. It is through this manner that teachers cannot just address students' need for improvement but to also reflect on their teaching performance for enhancement. Furthermore, punctuality demonstrates a teacher's professionalism and dependability, fostering trust and respect among colleagues, students, and parents, and emphasizing a strong commitment to their role as educators.

Extent of the Perceived Teaching Competency Level of Teachers in terms of Teaching for Independent Learning

Table 1.4 shows the students' perception of the extent of their teachers' teaching competency level in terms of teaching for independent learning which encompasses various indicators such as creating differentiated teaching strategies, enhancing students' self-esteem, allowing students to learn independently, encouraging students to think outside the box while guiding them simultaneously, giving students freedom to take

control over their learning, helping students hone their metacognition, eliciting students' responses and questions, and fostering inquiry and innovation in the lessons provided.

The results yield that teachers have 'Very High' competency level in terms of teaching for independent learning most especially on the following indicators which gained the highest mean scores (\overline{wx}) of 4.58, 4.57, 4.56, respectively, namely, encouraging students to ask questions and provide opportunities for them to analyze information, solve problems, and make informed decisions, encouraging students to learn beyond what is required and help and guide the students how to apply the concepts learned accountable for their performance, and creating teaching strategies that allow students to practice using concepts they need to understand (e.g., interactive discussion, collaboration, and independent learning.)

The use of questioning as scaffolding to independent learning is one of the effective means of encouraging students to become independent learners. The goal of employing questioning as scaffolding for independent learning is a progressive shift of responsibility from the teacher to the learner. To foster thinking, problem-solving abilities, and deeper comprehension, the teacher must build good classroom discourse, which includes asking higher order, open-ended questions and responding flexibly to student replies (Mullings, 2023). To further establish independent learning, teachers must allow the students to choose and manage their own learning, as well as explore and discover new things beyond the expected learning outcomes (United Nations International School of Hanoi, n.d.). This is because according to Ayish, and Deveci, (2019), students are more likely to accept responsibility for their learning when they understand their position as agents (the ones in control) of their own feelings, thoughts, and learning habits. To be autonomous learners, students must have some level of choice and control. Furthermore, as stipulated by Persaud (2024), students who are given the opportunity to study independently are empowered to take responsibility for their learning. Teachers may accommodate diverse learning styles and preferences by using approaches like interactive teaching strategies specifically personalized learning approach, which enable students to investigate subjects at their own pace. This individualized method helps students learn more effectively while also boosting their self-efficacy and confidence (Promethean, 2021).

Therefore, it is worth to note that the best way to ensure quality learning to students is when teachers meaningfully foster independent learning. As reflected in the gathered data, students find independent learning effective when teachers support their questioning and provide them chances to solve issues, assess data, and come to well-informed conclusions. Additionally, when given the freedom to study more than is necessary and are held responsible for their achievement, students learn most effectively. The key to effective independent learning is for teachers to develop instructional strategies (including interactive discussion, collaboration, and independent learning) that let students experience applying ideas they need to grasp.

Academic Performance of the Students in Diploma and Bachelor

Table 2.1 reveals the academic performance of students enrolled in Diploma programs and Baccalaureate degree courses during the first semester of the 2023-2024 school year. The findings indicate that a significant portion of the students—38.1% of the total sample—earned a grade range of 1.4 to 1.7, which was classified as “Very Good.” This suggests that these students demonstrated solid academic performance, achieving commendable results in their coursework. Additionally, 27.6% of the respondents scored between 1.0 and 1.3, earning an “Excellent” rating, reflecting the high level of academic achievement attained by this group of students.

The relatively high percentage of students receiving “Very Good” and “Excellent” remarks could be indicative of a positive learning environment and effective teaching strategies implemented in the institution. Several factors may contribute to these positive academic outcomes, including the quality of instruction, the commitment of teachers, the resources available for learning, and the students' personal motivation and study habits. These results suggest a high level of academic achievement within the sample, aligning with research that shows a positive correlation between effective teaching methods and student performance. For instance, studies have demonstrated that quality teaching practices such as clear instructional delivery, effective classroom management, and active student engagement are integral to fostering higher academic performance (Sanfo & Malgoubri, 2023). Furthermore, teacher competence in areas like instructional design and student support has been consistently linked with better student outcomes (Azzi & Ruggiero, 2020). These findings reinforce the importance of continuous teacher development and tailored pedagogical approaches in enhancing students' academic achievements across various academic levels.

Academic Performance of the Students in Senior High School

Table 2.2 shows the academic performance of Senior High School students during the school year 2023-2024. Evidently, the majority of the student-respondents, comprising 59.1% of the total number of respondents, garnered an ‘Outstanding’ remark on their grades ranging from 90-100, followed by 22.7% who obtained a grade range from 85-89, receiving a ‘Very Satisfactory’ remark.

This high academic performance can be attributed to several factors, including effective teaching methods, student motivation, and a supportive learning environment. Recent studies have highlighted the importance of a well-structured curriculum and student-centered teaching approaches in fostering academic success. For instance, a study by Garcia, et al. (2021), emphasizes that when students are provided with engaging and interactive learning experiences, their intrinsic motivation and academic outcomes improve significantly. Furthermore, academic performance is also influenced by students' emotional and psychological well-being. A study by Bacho, et al. (2020), suggests that students who feel supported both academically and emotionally are more likely to perform better in school. The availability of resources, such as well-trained teachers and effective learning materials, further contributes to the students' ability to perform at a high level

(Cruz & Caballes, 2022). These findings suggest that a combination of strong teaching practices, emotional support, and adequate resources may explain the positive academic outcomes observed among Senior High School students in this study.

Relationship between the Teachers' Perceived Teaching Competency Level on Diploma and Bachelor Students' Academic Performance

Table 3.1 reflects the relationship between the teachers' perceived teaching competency level and the academic performance of Diploma and Bachelor students. Based on the data, all variables had p-values greater than 0.05, implying no significant relationship exists between the teachers' perceived competency level and students' academic performances.

The result aligns with the findings of Canuto, Choycawe, and Pagdawan (2024), who determined the correlation results, indicating no significant association between proficiency in teaching influencing the performance of teachers and the achievement of students in the academe. As their study supposed, students' academic progress is not correlated with or predicted by the teacher's efficacy. However, it is imperative to acknowledge that academic accomplishment is a complex phenomenon shaped by many interrelated factors. In addition, as revealed in the study of Oredina and Ebueza (2020), there is no correlation between the academic performance of the students and teachers' competence; thus, the competence of the teachers in instruction cannot necessarily speculate the academic performance of the students.

Relationship between the Teachers' Perceived Teaching Competency Level on Senior High School Students' Academic Performance

Table 3.2 shows the relationship between the teachers' perceived teaching competency level and Senior High School students' academic performance. As can be gleaned from the table, all variables had p-values greater than 0.05, implying no significant relationship exists between the teachers' perceived competency level and Senior High School students' academic performances.

This is in line with the findings of Ebenezer (2023), who discovered no significant correlation between teachers' teaching experience or proficiency level and the students' academic performance. Hence, teachers' teaching approach does not significantly relate to secondary school students' academic performance. Furthermore, the study of Martin (2023) revealed no significant correlation in the academic performances among students taught by degree-holding and non-degree-holding teachers, teachers with different years of experience, and teachers with different hours of professional development. Thus, the academic performance and competence of the students will not always be determined by the performance level and number of years of experience of the teacher.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study on the perceived teaching competency levels in terms of instructional delivery, classroom management, commitment, and teaching for

independent learning revealed that while teachers are generally perceived to exhibit strong competencies in these areas, there is no significant relationship between these perceived competencies and the academic performance of both Diploma and Bachelor students as well as Senior High School students. This suggests that while teachers may be effective in their teaching practices, other factors beyond teaching competency might be influencing student performance, highlighting the need for a more holistic approach in assessing and enhancing educational outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researcher wholeheartedly recommends the following to the Educational Institution Administrators, teachers, and future researchers:

Educational Institution Administrators:

1. Encourage the implementation of regular professional development programs focusing on enhancing teachers' skills in areas such as instructional delivery, classroom management, and fostering independent learning in students.
2. Provide support for teachers to integrate up-to-date resources and teaching methodologies into their classrooms, ensuring that they are equipped to address students' diverse learning needs effectively.
3. Foster a collaborative learning environment where teachers can share best practices and strategies for improving student engagement, critical thinking, and performance.

Teachers:

4. Continuously engage in self-reflection and seek out professional development opportunities to refine teaching methods and adapt to the evolving educational landscape.
5. Incorporate differentiated instruction strategies and promote inquiry-based learning to encourage students' independence, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills.
6. Enhance classroom management techniques and maintain strong communication with students to create a conducive learning environment that supports both academic growth and personal development.

Future Researchers:

7. Conduct studies that explore other factors, beyond teaching competency, that may influence student academic performance, such as motivation, socio-economic factors, or learning environment.

8. Investigate the impact of specific teaching strategies and interventions on improving student academic outcomes, particularly in relation to skill development and independent learning.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher showed all the necessary ethical consideration on the entire duration of the study. Since humans were chosen as the study participants, confidentiality of information was observed. Ensuring the dignity and privacy of participants is also a must. Further, minimizing potential risk to the participants was observed.

The researcher followed the ethical protocols of Metro Dumaguete College. To ensure that the research topic was evidently sound significant and ethically correct, consultation was pursued. Moreover, the participants signed a consent form along with the full understanding of the risk and benefits of the study being conducted.

Acknowledgments

The researchers extend heartfelt gratitude to God Almighty for the wisdom and health bestowed, enabling the successful and pleasing completion of this research. It is through divine guidance that this endeavor has flourished, reflecting the power of perseverance and dedication. Each step of this journey has been a testament to the potential of education as a catalyst for growth and development. With faith and determination, the researchers have been inspired to explore the profound impact of teaching practices on student learning and academic success.

Sincere appreciation is also extended to Dr. Cristina P. Calisang, Mr. Jeckson B. Repollo, Ms. Erika Jane S. Cacaldo, Ms. Suzette Ceniza, Mr. Jerry A. Pariscal, Mr. Dexter D. Saycon, and Ms. Menche A. Tuting for their invaluable contributions, insights, and unwavering support throughout this journey. Each researcher's dedication and collaborative spirit have played a crucial role in enriching the study.

The researchers are also grateful to the educators and students who participated in this research, as their experiences and perspectives are the heart of this study. This collective effort underscores the importance of effective teaching in fostering academic achievement, paving the way for future improvements in educational practices.

REFERENCES

- Aderounmu, A. (2021). Why teachers should keep records of students' achievements (part 2). LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/why-teachers-should-keep-records-students-part-2-adeola-aderounmu>.
- Akram, M. (2019). Relationship between Students' Perceptions of Teachers Effectiveness and Student Achievement at Secondary School Level. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 41(2), 93-108.

- Anirudh, R. (2021). Why is it important to maintain a student tracking record? can student tracking improve learning?. Elearning Industry. <https://elearningindustry.com/why-maintain-student-tracking-record-to-improve-learning>.
- Ashraf, I. (2024). Punctuality among teachers. Cambridge. <https://connectedtot.com/2024/05/02/punctuality-among-teachers/#:~:text=In%20conclusion%2C%20the%20punctuality%20of,both%20teachers%20and%20students%20alike>.
- Ayish, N. & Deveci, T. (2019). Student perceptions of responsibility for their own learning and for supporting peers' learning in a project-based learning environment. *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*. 31 (2), 224-237. <http://www.isetl.org/ijtlhe/>
- Azzi, A., & Ruggiero, M. (2020). The role of teacher competence in improving academic achievement. *Education Research International*, 2020, 1-10.
- Bacho, S., Alvarado, G., & Dela Cruz, L. (2020). The impact of emotional well-being on academic performance of senior high school students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 29(4), 345-356.
- Canuto, P. P., Choycawen, M., & Pagdawan, R. (2024). The influence of teaching competencies on teachers' performance and students' academic achievement in primary science education. *Problems of Education in the 21st Century*, 82(1), 29– 47. <https://doi.org/10.33225/pec/24.82.29>
- Caroll, et al. (2022). Contextual learning: linking learning to the real world. *The Times Higher Education*. <https://www.timeshighereducation.com/campus/contextual-learning-linking-learning-real-world>.
- Cruz, M. L., & Caballes, C. P. (2022). Exploring the role of teacher competence in the academic performance of senior high school students. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 45(2), 112-120.
- Darling-Hammond, L., et al. (2020). Preparing educators for a changing world: Teacher learning for the future.
- Ebenezer, A. (2023). The effects of teachers' experience and qualifications on students' academic performance. <http://surl.li/mdeiew>
- Francisco, C. D. C. & Celon, L. C. (2020). Teacher's Instructional Practices and its Effects on students academic performance.
- Gamayao, M. D., & Binas, J. E. E. (2021). Teaching competence and pedagogical content.
- Garcia, R., Reyes, A., & Tan, D. (2021). Engagement and motivation in senior high school education: The role of interactive teaching methods. *Journal of Teaching and Learning in Education*, 35(1), 50-61.
- Gates, S. (2018). Benefits of collaboration. *neaToday*. <https://www.nea.org/professional-excellence/student-engagement/tools-tips/benefits-collaboration>.
- Kim, S., Raza, M., & Seidman, E. (2019). Improving 21st-century teaching skills: The key to knowledge of science teachers in the First District of Capiz, Philippines
- Lim, T. (2023). Problem-based learning: benefits, challenges, and the way forward. *ResearchGate*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/375671323_Problem-Based_Learning_Benefits_Challenges_and_the_Way_Forward/link/6555b999ce88b87031ea9f84/download?_tp=eyJjb250ZXh0Ijp7ImZpcnN0UGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2F0aW9uIiwicGFnZSI6InB1YmxpY2F0aW9uIn19
- Martin , A. A. (2023). Exploring the impact of teacher quality on student academic achievement
- McMillan, J.H. and Schumacher, S. (2001) *Research in Education. A Conceptual Introduction*. 5th Edition, Longman, Boston.
- Metropolitan State University of Denver (2022). Teaching by example and nonexample. Metropolitan State University. <https://www.msudenver.edu/early-bird/teaching-by-example-and->

- nonexample/#:~:text=Providing%20examples%20along%20with%20an,that%20students%20may%20already%20ha
- Mullings, C. (2023). Developing independent learning skills that improve outcomes. *Iris*.
- Munna, A. & Kalam, M. (2021). Impact of active learning strategy on the student engagement. *GNOSI: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Human Theory and Praxis*, 4(2), 96-99.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED614302.pdf>
- Navarro, M., & Santos, R. (2021). Challenges in Filipino teacher competency development.
- Oredina, N. & Ebueza R. (2020). Teachers' Competence and Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics: A Brief Cross-sectional Case in Don Mariano Marcos Memorial State University, Philippines. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(12A), 7766-7774.
DOI: 10.13189/ujer.2020.082564
- Padillo, G., Manguilimotan, R., Capuno, R., & Espiña, R. (2021). Professional development.
- Persaud, C. (2024). 25 effective instructional strategies for educators. *Top Hat*.
<https://tophat.com/blog/instructional-strategies/>.
- Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS). (2022). Professional development gaps among Filipino educators.
- Promethean (2021). 12 active learning strategies in the classroom. *Promethean Blog*.
<https://www.prometheanworld.com/gb/resource-centre/blogs/12-active-learning-strategies-in-the-classroom/>.
- Sanfo, S., & Malgoubri, A. (2021). Classroom management and its effects on student achievement: A study of secondary school classrooms. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(4), 997-1015.
- Sanfo, S., & Malgoubri, A. (2023). The three dimensions of teaching quality and their impact on student learning achievements. *Frontiers in Education*.
- Stronge, J. H. (2018). *Qualities of effective teachers*, 3rd edition. ERIC.
<https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED582452>
- Suneetha, E. (2020). Role of teachers as facilitators in learning. *Research Journal of English Language and Literature (RJELAL)*, 8(1), 71-71. <http://www.rjelal.com/8.S1.2020/71-72.pdf>
- UNESCO. (2023). *Global teacher shortage: Challenges and solutions in education*.
- United Nations International School of Hanoi (n.d.). How to encourage independent learning with 7 steps?. UNIS Hanoi.
<https://articles.unishanoi.org/how-to-encourage-independent-learning/#:~:text=To%20encourage%20independent%20learning%2C%20you,and%20discover%20things%20for%20themselves>.
- University of Michigan (2021). *Enhancing student learning: seven principles for good practice*. Center for Research on Learning and Teaching University of Michigan.
https://crlt.umich.edu/gsis/p4_6.